

8T – Strong Electroweak Unification

"That gleam in your eye tells me you have an idea." René Goscinny.

O Manor

August 21, 2021

Abstract:

The author present an additional way to unify the first three interactions, different and simpler than the one presented in the 8T thesis. Both ways are equivalent as they are constructed upon the primordial coupling series and aligning the net variation element. The new way does not include virtual exchanges of variation. Prediction of morphism at high energy is made. In particular, Photon onto W^+ , W^- Z Bosons and Gluon onto W^+ , W^- Z Bosons.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. In the 8T thesis, page twenty-one and twenty-two, the author presented the strong electroweak unification based on the primorial coupling series, which resulted in the accurate prediction of alignment on 26 variations. The unification was done via four exchanges, three real and virtual exchange. That was in rigor:

$$[8 + (1)] + 3 - (\mathbf{1v}): \quad [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 : [(24 * 5) + (3)] + \mathbf{3}$$

However, there is a simple way to do exact same thing without the virtual exchange of variation and taking the average of sum of exchanges. That is just by two real exchanges of variation from the third coupling term to the first coupling term. This will lead to the same result presented in the thesis, the unification of the strong electroweak interactions.

$$[8 + (1)] \rightarrow 8 + (1) + 2$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 3$$

The new, simpler way to unification does not include virtual exchange of variation;

$$8 + (1) + 2: [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 : [(24 * 5) + (3)] + \mathbf{3}$$

$$8 + (1) + 2 \rightarrow 8 + (3)$$

The two real exchanges between the third and the first will modify the same middle element the exact same manner as presented in the 8T thesis. The only term we can vary is the left, as we want to ensure duality among the forces; we cannot touch the net variation, marked in black;

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3.$$

We cannot vary the invariant three; the modification will be to the left term in the coupling series;

$$(8 * 3) + 2 = 26$$

The restrictions imposed on such variation on the strong are the same as presented in the thesis. I.e. it must be to an infinitesimal interval. The physical meaning of such equivalence relation in high energy is a morphism between the Bosons. A gluon morphism the weak interaction W^+, W^-, Z Bosons, and photon morphism to the W^+, W^-, Z Bosons.

$$\gamma \rightarrow W^+/W^-/Z$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + W^+$$

$$[8 + (g + 2)] \rightarrow 8 + W^+/W^-/Z$$

" Sign meant as it could morph to either three Bosons. We can make a prediction; "/

(1) At high energies there exist a morphism among the photon and the Gluon to the Bosons of the weak interaction. The Gluon at high energy can become a longer-range mediator (assuming we consider weak as longer ranged).

We can do it with any interaction in the primorial coupling series, but until they will be detected, we can only stick to the first well-known interactions.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad